

Classical Disappearance of the Ultraviolet Catastrophe
via Stochastic Boundary Conditions

Mason Biamonte

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1 Introduction

The Ultraviolet Catastrophe refers to the late 19th century conclusion that classical physics, together with the laws of electromagnetism, predicts that an ideal blackbody in thermal equilibrium emits an infinite amount of energy. The analysis involves assuming the electromagnetic field confined to a conducting cavity vanishes completely on the boundary. This gives rise to a countably infinite number of normal modes of the cavity, each of which behaves like an independent harmonic oscillator. The equipartition theorem, which states that independent harmonic oscillators will each equilibrate with the surrounding thermal bath and obtain average energy $k_B T$ [1, 2], independent of their individual natural frequencies, is then applied to each of these normal modes. This results in the prediction of an infinite total energy in the field [3, 4].

On December 14, 1900, Max Planck “resolved” this catastrophe by proposing the radical hypothesis that electromagnetic energy only occurs in multiples of a fundamental quantum [5]. Not only did this quantum hypothesis eliminate the infinite energy result and usher in the advent of quantum theory as a whole, it also agreed with the experimentally measured blackbody radiation spectrum.

In these notes, we show that the infinite energy result is not an inevitable prediction of classical physics *per se*. Instead, it is the direct result of a mathematical modeling mistake in which homogeneous boundary conditions are incorrectly used in a context with stochastic boundary conditions. In the original setup of blackbody radiation, the conducting cavity is placed in a thermal bath. This will produce thermal fluctuations in the charge and current distributions throughout the material forming the boundary of the cavity. These fluctuations will result in thermal radiation into the cavity. The electromagnetic radiation field inside the cavity will then have to satisfy stochastic boundary conditions consistent with the thermal fluctuations of the boundary charges and currents.

To simplify the analysis while preserving the essential physics involved, we study a system consisting of a one-dimensional scalar field (representing the electromagnetic field in the cavity) coupled to harmonic oscillators at the two boundary points (representing radiation sources throughout the boundary of the cavity), each of which is immersed in a thermal bath modeled via stochastic forcing. This is an acoustic analog of the original electromagnetic blackbody setup. We compute the thermal expectation of the energy in this scalar field and demonstrate that it is finite and non-zero.

2 Acoustic Ultraviolet Catastrophe

Consider a string of length L with constant linear mass density ρ held under tension κ . The displacement of the string $\phi(x, t)$ evolves according to the linear wave equation

$$(\partial_t^2 - c^2 \partial_x^2) \phi(x, t) = 0, x \in (-\frac{1}{2}L, +\frac{1}{2}L) \quad (1)$$

where $c \equiv \sqrt{\kappa/\rho}$ is the propagation speed of the waves in the string. We seek a separable solution $\phi(x, t) = X(x)Q(t)$ and obtain the spatial eigenvalue problem $X''(x) + k^2 X(x) = 0$. The spatial solutions that satisfy the homogeneous boundary conditions are $X_n(x) = \sin(2\pi n x/L)$. These are the normal modes of the string. The displacement of the string at time t is then

$$\phi(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q_n(t) \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nx}{L}\right) \quad (2)$$

The energy in the string is

$$E(t) = \int_{-\frac{1}{2}L}^{+\frac{1}{2}L} dx \left[\frac{1}{2}\rho (\partial_t \phi(x, t))^2 + \frac{1}{2}\kappa (\partial_x \phi(x, t))^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

Using the orthogonality of the normal modes, we have

$$E(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2} M \dot{q}_n^2(t) + \frac{1}{2} M \omega_n^2 q_n^2(t) \quad (4)$$

where $M \equiv \rho L$ is the total mass of the string. Each normal mode behaves like a simple harmonic oscillator. We now place these normal mode oscillators in contact with a thermal bath. The equipartition theorem [1] says that each quadratic degree of freedom placed in contact with a thermal bath will have expected energy equal to $k_B T/2$ in equilibrium. The thermal equilibrium expectation value of the energy in the string is

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_T [E(t)] = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathbb{E}_T \left[\frac{1}{2} M \dot{q}_n^2(t) \right] + \mathbb{E}_T \left[\frac{1}{2} M \omega_n^2 q_n^2(t) \right] = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} k_B T \quad (5)$$

The sum clearly diverges and we see, under these modeling assumptions, classical statistical mechanics predicts that a continuum field placed in thermal contact with a bath will exhibit infinite energy. This is the notorious Ultraviolet Catastrophe. We will show in the sections below that replacing the homogeneous boundary conditions with thermally–fluctuating boundary conditions allows a classical continuum field to equilibrate with a thermal bath and obtain finite equilibrium expected energy.

3 Physical System

We now change the homogeneous boundary conditions to stochastic boundary conditions generated by the physics of the thermal fluctuations. At the boundary points, $x = \pm \frac{1}{2}L$, the string is coupled to two mechanical oscillators with displacements $q_{\pm}(t)$, respectively. The string displacement must match the oscillators displacements at its boundary points

$$\phi(x = \pm \frac{1}{2}L, t) \equiv q_{\pm}(t) \quad (6)$$

We also assume that the oscillators' and string's initial displacements and momenta are zero

$$\begin{aligned}\phi(x, 0) = \partial_t \phi(x, 0) = 0, \quad x \in (-\tfrac{1}{2}L, +\tfrac{1}{2}L) \\ q_-(0) = \dot{q}_-(0) = q_+(0) = \dot{q}_+(0) = 0\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

Each oscillator has mass m , natural frequency ω_0 and is placed in thermal contact with a bath at temperature T . The two thermal baths have noise with correlations described by

$$\mathbb{E}_T [\xi_i(t)\xi_j(t')] \equiv \delta_{i,j} k_B T \Gamma \Omega \exp(-\Omega|t-t'|) \equiv \mathcal{C}(t, t')\tag{8}$$

where $\xi_i(t)$ is the random force exerted on oscillator i at time t due to the thermal fluctuations of the bath in which it is immersed. $\mathbb{E}_T[\cdot]$ is the expectation with respect to realizations of the bath(s) over the ensemble of thermal initializations at temperature T . We choose this noise model because it is the most simple and natural physically-realizable generalization of white noise with finite correlation time $\tau = 1/\Omega$ [7].

At $t = 0$, the oscillators are placed in thermal contact with their respective baths and begin to experience random, stochastic forcing. The motion of each oscillator is then

$$m\ddot{q}_\pm(t) + \int_0^t K(t-t')\dot{q}_\pm(t') dt' + m\omega_0^2 q_\pm(t) = \mp \kappa [[\partial_x \phi]]_{x=\pm \frac{1}{2}L}(t) + \xi_\pm(t)\tag{9}$$

where the memory kernel $K(t) \equiv \Gamma \Omega \exp(-\Omega t) \mathbf{1}_{t \geq 0}$ is specified by the fluctuation-dissipation theorem [7, 8, 9, 10] and $[[\partial_x \phi]]_{x=y}$ denotes the one-sided derivative at $x = y$. This type of boundary-coupled Hamiltonian system on a one-dimensional spatial domain has been studied in the context of infinite-dimensional “port-Hamiltonian” systems, where well-posedness and energy-balance conditions are derived for systems with boundary control and dissipation [6].

4 Laplace Transform

The Laplace transform is ideally suited to analyze the physical system above due to the fact that the system “turns on” at time $t = 0$. In addition, the Laplace transform converts partial derivatives and memory integrals into algebraic expressions, allowing us to write down explicit expressions for the string displacement in terms of the driving noise. Third, the noise model above plays especially nicely with the Laplace transform due to its exponential correlation structure.

The Laplace transform of the string’s displacement is given by

$$\mathcal{L}\{\phi(x, t)\}(s) \equiv \tilde{\phi}(x, s) \equiv \int_0^\infty dt e^{-st} \phi(x, t)\tag{10}$$

where $s \in \mathbb{C}$. The inverse Laplace transform gives a decomposition via integration over the Bromwich contour γ_B in the complex plane

$$\phi(x, t) \equiv \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\gamma_B} ds e^{st} \tilde{\phi}(x, s) \quad (11)$$

Plugging this decomposition into Eq. (1) gives the Laplace space wave equation

$$\left(\partial_x^2 - \frac{s^2}{c^2} \right) \tilde{\phi}(x, s) = 0, x \in (-\frac{1}{2}L, +\frac{1}{2}L) \quad (12)$$

which has general solution

$$\tilde{\phi}(x, s) = \tilde{F}(s) \cosh(sx/c) + \tilde{G}(s) \sinh(sx/c) \quad (13)$$

Using the Laplace transform of the boundary conditions in Eqs. (6) gives

$$\tilde{\phi}(x = \pm \frac{1}{2}L, s) = \tilde{F}(s) \cosh(sL/2c) \pm \tilde{G}(s) \sinh(sL/2c) = \tilde{q}_{\pm}(s) \quad (14)$$

This allows us to write $\tilde{F}(s)$ and $\tilde{G}(s)$ purely in terms of the Laplace transforms of the boundary oscillators' trajectories $\tilde{q}_{\pm}(s)$

$$\tilde{\phi}(x, s) = \frac{\tilde{q}_+(s) \sinh(s(x + \frac{1}{2}L)/c) - \tilde{q}_-(s) \sinh(s(x - \frac{1}{2}L)/c)}{\sinh(sL/c)} \quad (15)$$

Now, we take the Laplace transform of the string–oscillators coupling (trajectory) equations so that we can write the Laplace transforms of the oscillator trajectories purely in terms of the driving noise. This step will allow us to write the field energy purely in terms of the driving noise and then the thermal expectation of the field energy can be obtained by taking the expectation and invoking the exponential form of the noise correlation. The first step is to write down the Laplace transform of the one–sided derivatives of the string displacement responsible for the force exerted on the oscillators by the field

$$\tilde{f}_{\pm}(s) \equiv \mathcal{L}\{[\partial_x \phi]_{x=\pm l}(t)\}(s) = \lim_{x \rightarrow \pm \frac{1}{2}L^{\mp}} \partial_x \tilde{\phi}(x, s) \quad (16)$$

Explicitly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{f}_+(s) &= (s/c) [\tilde{q}_+(s) \cosh(sL/c) - \tilde{q}_-(s)] / \sinh(sL/c) \\ \tilde{f}_-(s) &= (s/c) [\tilde{q}_+(s) - \tilde{q}_-(s) \cosh(sL/c)] / \sinh(sL/c) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The Laplace transform of the coupling/trajectory Eqs. (9) are

$$\left[m(s^2 + \omega_0^2) + \frac{\Gamma\Omega s}{s + \Omega} \right] \tilde{q}_\pm(s) \equiv \tilde{A}(s)\tilde{q}_\pm(s) = \mp\kappa\tilde{f}_\pm(s) + \tilde{\xi}_\pm(s) \quad (18)$$

where the noise correlation in Laplace frequency space is

$$\mathbb{E}_T \left[\tilde{\xi}_i(s)\tilde{\xi}_j(s') \right] = \frac{\delta_{i,j}\Gamma\Omega k_B T (2\Omega + s + s')}{(s + s')(s + \Omega)(s' + \Omega)} \equiv \delta_{i,j}\tilde{K}(s, s') \quad (19)$$

Defining $\tilde{A}_+(s) \equiv \tilde{A}(s) + \frac{\kappa s}{c} \coth\left(\frac{sL}{c}\right)$ and $\tilde{A}_-(s) \equiv \frac{\kappa s}{c} \operatorname{csch}\left(\frac{sL}{c}\right)$, we arrive at the 2×2 system

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{A}_+(s) & -\tilde{A}_-(s) \\ -\tilde{A}_-(s) & \tilde{A}_+(s) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{q}_+(s) \\ \tilde{q}_-(s) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\xi}_+(s) \\ \tilde{\xi}_-(s) \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

which gives

$$\tilde{q}_\pm(s) = \tilde{d}^{-1}(s)\tilde{A}_+(s)\tilde{\xi}_\pm(s) + \tilde{d}^{-1}(s)\tilde{A}_-(s)\tilde{\xi}_\mp(s) \equiv \tilde{B}_+(s)\tilde{\xi}_\pm(s) + \tilde{B}_-(s)\tilde{\xi}_\mp(s) \quad (21)$$

where $\tilde{d}(s) \equiv \tilde{A}_+(s)^2 - \tilde{A}_-(s)^2$ and $\tilde{B}_\pm(s) \equiv \tilde{d}^{-1}(s)\tilde{A}_\pm(s)$. The punchline is that we have been able to write the stochastic boundary oscillator trajectories purely in terms of the driving noise while also including the coupling to the string. Since in Eq. (15) we have the string displacement written purely in terms of the boundary oscillators' displacement, this means that we have the string displacement purely in terms of the driving noise. In the next section, we use this result to compute the $t \rightarrow \infty$ equilibrium limit of the thermal expectation value of the energy in the string and show that is finite.

5 Thermal Equilibrium Energy

Now that we have the Laplace transform of the string displacement purely in terms of the driving noise terms, we can compute the thermal expectation of the energy $E(t)$ in the string

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_T [E(t)] &= \mathbb{E}_T \left[\int_{-\frac{1}{2}L}^{+\frac{1}{2}L} dx \rho (\partial_t \phi(x, t))^2 + \kappa (\partial_x \phi(x, t))^2 \right] \\ &= \rho \int_{-\frac{1}{2}L}^{+\frac{1}{2}L} dx \int_{\gamma_B} ds \int_{\gamma'_B} ds' e^{(s+s')t} \left((s \cdot s') \mathbb{E}_T \left[\tilde{\phi}(x, s)\tilde{\phi}(x, s') \right] + c^2 \mathbb{E}_T \left[\partial_x \tilde{\phi}(x, s)\partial_x \tilde{\phi}(x, s') \right] \right) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

To evaluate this double contour integral, we first compute the thermal expectation value occurring inside the integrand above. Let's start with the thermal expectation value of the product of the Laplace transform of the string displacement at x evaluated at s and s' .

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}_T \left[\tilde{\phi}(x, s) \tilde{\phi}(x, s') \right] = \\ & \mathbb{E}_T \left[\left(\frac{\tilde{q}_+(s) \sinh\left(\frac{s(x+L/2)}{c}\right) - \tilde{q}_-(s) \sinh\left(\frac{s(x-L/2)}{c}\right)}{\sinh(sL/c)} \right) \left(\frac{\tilde{q}_+(s') \sinh\left(\frac{s'(x+L/2)}{c}\right) - \tilde{q}_-(s') \sinh\left(\frac{s'(x-L/2)}{c}\right)}{\sinh(s'L/c)} \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

We need to compute all of the $\mathbb{E}_T [\tilde{q}_i(s) \tilde{q}_j(s')]$. Here they are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_T [\tilde{q}_+(s) \tilde{q}_+(s')] &= \mathbb{E}_T [\tilde{q}_-(s) \tilde{q}_-(s')] = \left(\tilde{B}_+(s) \tilde{B}_+(s') + \tilde{B}_-(s) \tilde{B}_-(s') \right) \tilde{K}(s, s') \\ \mathbb{E}_T [\tilde{q}_+(s) \tilde{q}_-(s')] &= \mathbb{E}_T [\tilde{q}_-(s) \tilde{q}_+(s')] = \left(\tilde{B}_+(s) \tilde{B}_-(s') + \tilde{B}_-(s) \tilde{B}_+(s') \right) \tilde{K}(s, s') \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Defining $D_+(s, s') \equiv \tilde{B}_+(s) \tilde{B}_+(s') + \tilde{B}_-(s) \tilde{B}_-(s')$ and $D_-(s, s') \equiv \tilde{B}_+(s) \tilde{B}_-(s') + \tilde{B}_-(s) \tilde{B}_+(s')$, gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}_T \left[\tilde{\phi}(x, s) \tilde{\phi}(x, s') \right] = \\ & \frac{\tilde{K}(s, s')}{\sinh\left(\frac{sL}{c}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{s'L}{c}\right)} \left[\tilde{D}_+(s, s') \left(\sinh\left(\frac{s(x+L/2)}{c}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{s'(x+L/2)}{c}\right) + \sinh\left(\frac{s(x-L/2)}{c}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{s'(x-L/2)}{c}\right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \tilde{D}_-(s, s') \left(\sinh\left(\frac{s(x+L/2)}{c}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{s'(x-L/2)}{c}\right) + \sinh\left(\frac{s(x-L/2)}{c}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{s'(x+L/2)}{c}\right) \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Now we compute the thermal expectation of the product of the derivatives of the string displacement at x evaluated at s and s' . We start by first writing down the derivative

$$\partial_x \tilde{\phi}(x, s) = \frac{s}{c} \left[\frac{\tilde{C}_+(s) \cosh(s(x + \frac{1}{2}L)/c) - \tilde{C}_-(s) \cosh(s(x - \frac{1}{2}L)/c)}{\sinh(sL/c)} \right] \quad (26)$$

which gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}_T \left[\partial_x \tilde{\phi}(x, s) \partial_x \tilde{\phi}(x, s') \right] = \\ & \frac{\tilde{K}(s, s')(s \cdot s'/c^2)}{\sinh\left(\frac{sL}{c}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{s'L}{c}\right)} \left[\tilde{D}_+(s, s') \left(\cosh\left(\frac{s(x+L/2)}{c}\right) \cosh\left(\frac{s'(x+L/2)}{c}\right) + \cosh\left(\frac{s(x-L/2)}{c}\right) \cosh\left(\frac{s'(x-L/2)}{c}\right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \tilde{D}_-(s, s') \left(\cosh\left(\frac{s(x+L/2)}{c}\right) \cosh\left(\frac{s'(x-L/2)}{c}\right) + \cosh\left(\frac{s(x-L/2)}{c}\right) \cosh\left(\frac{s'(x+L/2)}{c}\right) \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

So the thermal expectation of the energy in the string is

$$\mathbb{E}_T [E(t)] = -\frac{\rho c \Gamma \Omega k_B T}{2\pi^2} \int_{\gamma_B} ds \int_{\gamma'_B} ds' \frac{e^{(s+s')t} (s \cdot s') \tilde{D}_+(s, s') (2\Omega + s + s') \sinh\left(\frac{(s+s')L}{c}\right)}{\sinh\left(\frac{sL}{c}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{s'L}{c}\right) (s + s')^2 (s + \Omega)(s' + \Omega)} \quad (28)$$

Expanding $\tilde{D}_+(s, s')$ allows us to obtain the final explicit form of the integrand

$$\tilde{D}_+(s, s') = \frac{\tilde{A}_+(s)\tilde{A}_+(s') + \tilde{A}_-(s)\tilde{A}_-(s')}{\tilde{d}(s)\tilde{d}(s')} = \frac{\tilde{A}_+(s)\tilde{A}_+(s') + \tilde{A}_-(s)\tilde{A}_-(s')}{\left(\tilde{A}_+(s)^2 - \tilde{A}_-(s)^2\right)\left(\tilde{A}_+(s')^2 - \tilde{A}_-(s')^2\right)} \quad (29)$$

Defining

$$\tilde{A}'_{\pm}(s) \equiv \sinh(sL/c)\tilde{A}_{\pm}(s), \quad \tilde{A}''_{\pm}(s) \equiv (s + \Omega)\tilde{A}'_{\pm}(s) \quad (30)$$

allows us to rewrite the thermal expectation value of the energy in the string as

$$\mathbb{E}_T [E(t)] = -\frac{\rho c \Gamma \Omega k_B T}{2\pi^2} \iint_{\gamma_B, \gamma'_B} ds ds' \frac{e^{(s+s')t} (s \cdot s') (2\Omega + s + s') \sinh\left(\frac{(s+s')L}{c}\right) \left(\tilde{A}''_+(s)\tilde{A}''_+(s') + \tilde{A}''_-(s)\tilde{A}''_-(s')\right)}{(s+s')^2 \left(\tilde{A}''_+(s)^2 - \tilde{A}''_-(s)^2\right) \left(\tilde{A}''_+(s')^2 - \tilde{A}''_-(s')^2\right)} \quad (31)$$

where

$$\tilde{A}''_+(s) = m(s^2 + \omega_0^2)(s + \Omega) + \Gamma \Omega s + \frac{\kappa s(s + \Omega)}{c} \cosh\left(\frac{sL}{c}\right), \quad \tilde{A}''_-(s) = \frac{\kappa s}{c}(s + \Omega) \quad (32)$$

There are two main contributions to the contour integral above: (1) the zeros of $\tilde{A}''_+(s)^2 - \tilde{A}''_-(s)^2$, which will determine the non-equilibrium relaxation to equilibrium and (2) the second order pole at $s' = -s$, which determines the equilibrium energy. To prove that the poles due to the zeros of (1) do not contribute to the equilibrium limit nor cause exponential blow-up, we need to prove that these zeros all lie in the left-half plane.

We start by defining $\tilde{H}(s) \equiv \tilde{A}''_+(s)^2 - \tilde{A}''_-(s)^2$ and observing that we can factor this expression as

$$\tilde{H}(s) = \left(\tilde{A}''_+(s) + \tilde{A}''_-(s)\right) \left(\tilde{A}''_+(s) - \tilde{A}''_-(s)\right) \equiv \tilde{J}_+(s)\tilde{J}_-(s) \quad (33)$$

where $\tilde{J}_{\pm}(s) = m(s^2 + \omega_0^2)(s + \Omega) + \Gamma \Omega s + \frac{\kappa s(s + \Omega)}{c} (\cosh(\frac{sL}{c}) \pm 1)$. Any zero of \tilde{H} must be a zero of either \tilde{J}_+ or \tilde{J}_- . Then, it suffices to show that neither \tilde{J}_+ nor \tilde{J}_- has zeros in the closed right half-plane $\mathbb{H}_r \equiv \{s \in \mathbb{C} \mid \text{Re}[s] \geq 0\}$. Note that \tilde{J}_{\pm} are entire functions.

Let's now show that neither $\tilde{J}_+(s)$ nor $\tilde{J}_-(s)$ vanishes on the imaginary axis. This means there are no zeros on the imaginary axis. Let $s = i\omega$ with $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$. Then $\cosh(sL/c) = \cos(\omega L/c)$ is real and satisfies $|\cos(\omega L/c)| \leq 1$. Separating real and imaginary parts of $\tilde{J}_{\pm}(i\omega)$ shows that the polynomial terms in $i\omega$ contribute non-vanishing imaginary parts except possibly at $\omega = 0$. At $\omega = 0$, $\tilde{J}_{\pm}(0) = m\omega_0^2 \Omega \neq 0$. Even if $\omega = \omega_0$ and $\omega_0 = c/L$, which would be a bizarre and precise numerical coincidence between the natural frequency of the boundary oscillators and that of the

normal modes of the string, $\tilde{J}_-(i\omega_0) = i\Gamma\Omega\omega_0 \neq 0$. Hence $\tilde{J}_\pm(i\omega) \neq 0$ for all $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$.

We use the argument principle to show that there are no zeros in the closed right half-plane \mathbb{H}_r . We use a closed contour C consisting of a semi-circular arc C_R of “large” radius R in \mathbb{H}_r and a straight line down the imaginary axis C_I from iR to $-iR$. We can count the number of zeros inside this contour by tracking the cumulative change in the argument $\Delta\Phi$ for both \tilde{J}_+ and \tilde{J}_- . The number of zeros is $N = \Delta\Phi/2\pi$. Thus, if the cumulative change in the argument vanishes, there are no zeros inside this contour and we can take the limit as $R \rightarrow \infty$ to extend this to \mathbb{H}_r [12].

Let’s start with the semi-circular arc C_R . Parametrize this arc by $s = e^{i\theta}$ where $\theta \in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$. In the $R \rightarrow \infty$ limit, the functions are dominated by $(\kappa s^2/2c) \exp[-sL/c]$. The cumulative change in the argument over the arc due to this term is $\Delta\Phi_R = \Delta\Phi_R(\pi/2) - \Delta\Phi_R(-\pi/2) = 2\pi + 2RL/c$.

Now we calculate the cumulative change in the argument over C_I . Parametrize this straight line down the imaginary axis by $s = i\omega$ where ω runs from R to $-R$. We inherit the value of the argument from the endpoint of the arc at $s = iR$ and have $\Phi_I(R) = \pi + RL/c$. Now we can evaluate the argument at the origin to see how much the argument has changed as we move down to the midpoint of C_I . Since $\tilde{J}_\pm(0) = m\omega_0^2\Omega$, $\Phi_I(0) = 0$ and the argument has decreased by $\pi + RL/c$. Thus, $\Phi_I(-R) = -\pi - RL/c$ and the total cumulative change of the argument along C_I is $\Delta\Phi_I = -2\pi - 2RL/c$.

The cumulative change in the argument over the full contour C vanishes and there are no zeros contained within. Taking the $R \rightarrow \infty$ limit tells us that there are no zeros of \tilde{J}_\pm in \mathbb{H}_r . Since we have already shown that these functions also do not have zeros on the imaginary axis itself, all zeros of \tilde{J}_\pm must lie in the open left half-plane $\mathbb{H}_l \equiv \{s \in \mathbb{C} | \text{Re}[s] < 0\}$. This means all the zeros have negative real part and when we compute the residues of the energy integral in Eq. (27), they will all vanish in the $t \rightarrow \infty$ limit. As a result, the only residue we need to compute for the equilibrium limit is due to the second order pole at $s' = -s$. We rewrite the integral here using the notation introduced above for clarity

$$\mathbb{E}_T[E(t)] = -\frac{\rho c \Gamma \Omega k_B T}{2\pi^2} \iint_{\gamma_B, \gamma'_B} ds ds' \frac{e^{(s+s')t} (s \cdot s') (2\Omega + s + s') \sinh\left(\frac{(s+s')L}{c}\right) \left(\tilde{A}''_+(s)\tilde{A}''_+(s') + \tilde{A}''_-(s)\tilde{A}''_-(s')\right)}{(s+s')^2 \tilde{J}_+(s)\tilde{J}_-(s)\tilde{J}_+(s')\tilde{J}_-(s')} \quad (34)$$

So let’s compute the thermal equilibrium expectation value of the energy in the string by evaluating the residue due to the second order pole at $s' = -s$

$$\text{Res}[s' = -s] = \lim_{s' \rightarrow -s} \frac{\partial}{\partial s'} \left[\frac{e^{s't} s' (2\Omega + s + s') \sinh\left(\frac{(s+s')L}{c}\right) \tilde{M}(s, s')}{\tilde{J}_+(s')\tilde{J}_-(s')} \right] \quad (35)$$

where $\tilde{M}(s, s') \equiv \left(\tilde{A}''_+(s)\tilde{A}''_+(s') + \tilde{A}''_-(s)\tilde{A}''_-(s')\right)$. The only term that is going to survive the partial derivative with respect to s' is the term where the derivative acts directly on $\sinh((s+s')L/c)$. So the residue is

$$\text{Res} [s' = -s] = \lim_{s' \rightarrow -s} \frac{L e^{s't} s' (2\Omega + s + s') \cosh\left(\frac{(s+s')L}{c}\right) \tilde{M}(s, s')}{c \tilde{J}_+(s') \tilde{J}_-(s')} = -\frac{2\Omega L}{c} \frac{s e^{-st} \tilde{M}(s, -s)}{\tilde{J}_+(-s) \tilde{J}_-(-s)} \quad (36)$$

So the $t \rightarrow \infty$ limit of the thermal expectation value of the energy in the string is

$$E_\infty \equiv \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}_T [E(t)] = \frac{2\rho\Gamma\Omega^2 L k_B T}{\pi} i \int_{\gamma_B} ds \frac{s^2 \left(\tilde{A}_+''(s) \tilde{A}_+''(-s) + \tilde{A}_-''(s) \tilde{A}_-''(-s) \right)}{\tilde{J}_+(s) \tilde{J}_-(s) \tilde{J}_+(-s) \tilde{J}_-(-s)} \quad (37)$$

From the analysis of the properties of $\tilde{J}_\pm(s)$ above, there is a rectangular strip of analyticity of this integrand surrounding the imaginary axis. This allows us to deform the Bromwich contour to the imaginary axis itself. Since there are no exponential factors in the integrand, we no longer need to close the Bromwich contour in the left half-plane [11].

We parametrize the integral using $s = i\omega$ with $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$. The equilibrium energy in the string becomes

$$E_\infty = \frac{2\rho\Gamma\Omega^2 L k_B T}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\omega \frac{\omega^2 \left(\tilde{A}_+''(i\omega) \tilde{A}_+''(-i\omega) + \tilde{A}_-''(i\omega) \tilde{A}_-''(-i\omega) \right)}{\tilde{J}_+(i\omega) \tilde{J}_-(i\omega) \tilde{J}_+(-i\omega) \tilde{J}_-(-i\omega)} \quad (38)$$

Denote the integrand by $\tilde{I}(\omega)$ and define the constant in front of the integral to be $C(T) \equiv 2\rho\Gamma\Omega^2 L k_B T / \pi$. Let $\omega = R \gg 1$ be some large frequency value. Then, we have

$$E_\infty \leq C(T) \left[\int_{-R}^R d\omega |\tilde{I}(\omega)| + 2 \int_R^\infty d\omega |\tilde{I}(\omega)| \right] \quad (39)$$

Since $\tilde{I}(\omega)$ is the quotient of entire functions and $\tilde{J}_\pm(i\omega) \neq 0$ for all $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$, the integrand is continuous on $[-R, R]$. By the Extreme Value Theorem, any continuous function on a compact interval is bounded and so we have

$$\int_{-R}^R d\omega |\tilde{I}(\omega)| \leq 2RC_1 < \infty \quad (40)$$

where C_1 is some positive constant. Now we need to understand the asymptotic behavior of $\tilde{I}(\omega)$ so we can bound the remaining tail integral from R to ∞ . For large ω , $\tilde{A}_\pm''(\pm i\omega)$ are dominated by $\mp im\omega^3$, respectively. $\tilde{A}_-''(\pm i\omega)$ are both dominated by $-\kappa\omega^2/c$. So the numerator of $\tilde{I}(\omega)$ scales like ω^8 . The $\tilde{J}_\pm(\pm i\omega)$ are also dominated by $\mp im\omega^3$ and so the denominator of $\tilde{I}(\omega)$ scales like ω^{12} . As a result, we have the limit

$$\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{\tilde{I}(\omega)}{1/\omega^4} \right| = C_2 < \infty \quad (41)$$

where C_2 is some positive constant. This means that for all $\epsilon > 0$, there exists an R_ϵ such that for all $\omega > R_\epsilon$

$$\left| \frac{\tilde{I}(\omega)}{1/\omega^4} \right| < C_2 + \epsilon \quad (42)$$

Let $C_3 \equiv C_2 + \epsilon$. Then $|\tilde{I}(\omega)| < C_3/\omega^4$ for all $\omega > R_\epsilon$. So now we have

$$E_\infty \leq C(T) \left[\int_{-R_\epsilon}^{R_\epsilon} d\omega |\tilde{I}(\omega)| + 2 \int_{R_\epsilon}^{\infty} d\omega |\tilde{I}(\omega)| \right] \leq C(T) \left[2R_\epsilon C_1 + \frac{2C_3}{3R_\epsilon^3} \right] < \infty \quad (43)$$

and the thermal equilibrium energy in the string is finite. Note that in the white noise limit $\Omega \rightarrow \infty$, the upper bound itself diverges and we no longer have finite energy in the string. The finite-time correlated colored noise is essential in the finite equilibrium energy result.

We still need to show that the thermal equilibrium energy in the string is greater than zero. If the energy is zero, then we would have a trivial situation where no energy gets transferred to the string. In this trivial situation, the finite energy result would not carry any meaning. To show that this is not the case, or, rather, to identify the physical parameter regimes in which it is the case, we start with the integral in Eq. (38) for the equilibrium energy

$$\begin{aligned} E_\infty &= 2C(T) \int_0^\infty d\omega \frac{\omega^2 \left(|\tilde{A}_+''(i\omega)|^2 + |\tilde{A}_-''(i\omega)|^2 \right)}{|\tilde{J}_+(i\omega)|^2 |\tilde{J}_-(i\omega)|^2} \\ &\geq 2C(T) \int_0^\infty d\omega \frac{\omega^2 |\tilde{A}_-''(i\omega)|^2}{|\tilde{J}_+(i\omega)|^2 |\tilde{J}_-(i\omega)|^2} = \frac{2\kappa^2 C(T)}{c^2} \int_0^\infty d\omega \frac{\omega^4 (\omega^2 + \Omega^2)}{|\tilde{J}_+(i\omega)|^2 |\tilde{J}_-(i\omega)|^2} \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Since the integrand is positive and non-zero for all $\omega \geq 0$, and we already know that the integral converges, it immediately follows that $E_\infty > 0$ for all non-zero coupling/tension values $\kappa > 0$.

6 Conclusion and Future Directions

By explicitly modeling the stochastic boundary conditions on the linear wave equation, we have shown that the thermal equilibrium energy in a 1D scalar field is finite. This directly contradicts the standard Ultraviolet Catastrophe result, which is obtained by incorrectly employing homogeneous boundary conditions in a context where the boundaries experience thermal fluctuations.

To be clear, this analysis does not claim to reproduce the blackbody radiation spectrum and, in turn, does not claim to replace Planck's quantum hypothesis with some classical mechanism. Instead, we have only shown that the standard ultraviolet divergence of the energy in a scalar field is consequence of a mathematical modeling mistake where the incorrect boundary conditions are used.

Since we have succeeded in demonstrating a phenomenon which has previously been considered to have a purely quantum origin with an explicit classical system, we can immediately ask if this same classical system can display any other quantum-like phenomena. Because we already have

a precise mathematical formulation of the physical system, we can compute the equilibrium correlation between the boundary oscillators' displacements for time separations less than that of the wave travel time across the string. A non-vanishing correlation in this regime will provide insight into how statistical non-locality can arise between spatially-separated massive bodies, via the interaction between coherent waves and stochastic (thermal) fluctuations.

The model itself can also be made more realistic by extending to a three-dimensional electromagnetic setting. This can be achieved by using a 3D rectangular waveguide and coupling the field to electromagnetic damped oscillator circuits on the boundaries. This will bring the analysis closer to the original Ultraviolet Catastrophe context.

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